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A STUDY OF SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE IN RELATION TO ACHIEVEMENT IN SCIENCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN COIMBATORE EDUCATIONAL DISTRICT

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Abstract

As a nation, the India is failing to compete globally in academic achievement. The problem addressed in the current study is twofold, with both components dealing with student underachievement. The first concern is that students are failing to reach individual potential, and second that the country is failing in global academic competition. The search for valid solutions to remediate underachievement has yielded non-traditional methods of internal motivation and resiliency with emotional and even spiritual implications. Consequently research needs to be conducted to verify if in fact a student's spiritual intelligence acts as an internal motivator that encourages or predicts his or her achievement. Therefore, the current study investigated was the effect of a secondary student's spiritual intelligence on his or her achievement in Science subjects. The study aimed to study of spiritual intelligence in relation achievement in science among secondary school students. The study was conducted on a sample of 300 secondary school students. Sampling was done through proportionate stratified technique giving dual representation to the various strata like sex, location, type of institute, medium of institute, religion, community etc. The findings reveal that the causes of spiritual intelligence among the secondary school students differ on the basis of Gender at different board; this may be due to the fact that the male and female students perceive spiritual intelligence merely as a subject and does not provide equal attention as to other subject.

Keywords: Spiritual Intelligence; Achievement; Education.

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1. Introduction

Spiritual intelligence is a higher dimension of intelligence that activates the qualities and capabilities of the authentic self (or the soul), in the form of wisdom, compassion, integrity, joy, love, creativity, and peace. Spiritual intelligence results in a sense of deeper meaning and purpose, combined with improvements in a wide range of important life skills and work skills.

Analysis of Spiritual Intelligence

The following equation analyses SQ in terms of IQ and EQ in association with the state of presence:

$$SQ = P (IQ+EQ), \text{ where } P = \text{presence}$$

This equation means that SQ equals IQ and EQ magnified by the power of presence. Thus spiritual intelligence results when intellectual and emotional intelligence are exercised in the state of presence.

1.1. Need for the Study

Spiritual Intelligence is to 'realize' who you are and to live life in that awareness in the society. Spiritual intelligence expands your capacity to understand others at the deepest level. Spiritual understanding allows you to discern both the 'true cause' of behavior without judgment, and serve the 'true needs' of others until they themselves learn to meet their own needs.

The current study is to understand how spiritual intelligence helps students to understand science and help them to understand the deep innate value of science. Scope of the spiritual Intelligence study helps to identify the purpose of spiritual intelligence, how it helps to align personal value with purpose, understand how science can be used to enhance our lives etc.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

The problem for the present study is entitled as, "A STUDY OF SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE IN RELATION TO ACHIEVEMENT IN SCIENCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS".

1.3. Objectives of the Study

1.3.1. General Objectives

- 1) A study of spiritual intelligence in relation achievement in science among secondary school students.

1.3.2. Specific Objectives

Based on the general objectives of the study the following specific objectives were considered.

- 1) To find out the spiritual intelligence and achievement in science among Secondary School Students.
- 2) To find out the relationship between spiritual intelligence and achievement in science among Secondary School Student.
- 3) To find out the variance in Spiritual Intelligence based on the personal variables of Secondary School Students.
- 4) To find out the variance in Spiritual Intelligence based on hobbies of Secondary School Students.

1.4. Historical Background of the Topic

In the present study investigator has adopted the Survey research design. Survey research employs questionnaires and interviews to ask people to provide information about themselves-their attitudes and beliefs, demographics (age, gender, income, Locality and so on) and other facts and past or intended future behaviors. The Survey method may be classified into several categories such as case study, documentary analysis, developmental studies, follow up studies and correlation study. In this study investigator adopted the descriptive survey method. The present study examined the Study of spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science among secondary school students. In this study descriptive correlation study, 300 secondary school students from 8 different schools from Coimbatore district, randomly selected and studied. Instruments included demographic information on checklist and questionnaire based on spiritual intelligence as well as academic achievement. Data collected and analyzed by statistical software, T-test, F-test and Pearson correlation.

1.5. Hypothesis Formed

Based on the general and specific objectives of the study the following hypotheses were formulated in this present study.

- 1) There will be significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and achievement in science among the selected Secondary School Students.
- 2) There will be significant mean score difference in spiritual intelligence between male and female of the selected Secondary School Students.
- 3) There will be significant mean score difference in spiritual intelligence between the based in Locality (Rural & Urban) among the selected Secondary School Students.
- 4) There will be significant mean score difference in spiritual intelligence between the groups based on Annual income of the family among the selected Secondary School Students.
- 5) There will be significant mean score difference in spiritual intelligence between the groups based on Habit of Reading News paper (Regularly & Occasionally) among the selected Secondary School Students.
- 6) There will be significant mean score difference in spiritual intelligence between the groups based on Habits of Watching TV (Regularly & Occasionally) among the selected Secondary School Students.
- 7) There will be significant mean score difference in spiritual intelligence between the groups based on Habit of hearing Music (Regularly & Occasionally) among the selected Secondary School Students.

- 8) There will be significant mean score difference in spiritual intelligence between the groups based on Habit of Playing Games (Regularly & Occasionally) among the selected Secondary School Students.
- 9) There will be significant mean score difference in spiritual intelligence between the groups based on Habit of using internet (Occasionally & Never) among the selected Secondary School Students.

1.6. Delimitations of the Study

No research study can be carried out without certain limitations due to place, people, circumstances and time limitations are those conditions beyond the control of the investigator that may place restrictions on the conclusions of the study and their application to other situations. The present research has following limitations,

- 1) With a limited period of time, it is not possible to conduct the research study in a large scale. So the study was limited to 8 schools around Coimbatore District.
- 2) This study was conducted on a sample of 300 students only.
- 3) It is limited in Coimbatore District only.
- 4) The study is not a representative of the entire state.
- 5) Thirty questions only have been chosen for the present study
- 6) The investigation is limited to secondary school students only.

1.7. Review of Literature

Hamid Saremi et al. (2015)¹ conducted a study to identify and determine the relationship between spiritual intelligence and organizational commitment in male teachers at elementary schools. The results showed that there was not a significant correlation between total spiritual intelligence and total organizational commitment.

Ahmad M Mahasneh et al. (2015)², This study was aimed at identifying the level of spiritual intelligence and its correlation with personality traits among a group of Jordanian undergraduate students. The most important finding that can be drawn from this study was that a positive and statistically significant relationship exists between spiritual intelligence dimensions (critical existential thinking, personal meaning production, transcendental awareness, and conscious state expansion) and personality traits (neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness)

Mahdi Dasht Bozorgi et al. (2016)³, The purpose of this study was to investigate the role of spiritual intelligence and coping strategies in the mental health of students. The findings indicate that there is a significant and negative relationship between spiritual intelligence and mental disorders. In addition, there is a significant and negative relationship between problem-focused coping strategies and mental disorders.

Haikal Anuar Adnan et al. (2014)⁴, The study was carried out to identify the differences of emotional intelligence and religious orientation between students in government secondary schools and religious secondary schools. The results showed that there were differences in

emotional intelligence but no difference was found in religious orientation between students from government secondary schools and religious secondary schools.

Maryam Keshtegar et al. (2015)⁵, The study aimed to examine the relationship among emotional intelligence, spiritual intelligence and resilience of students at University of Zabol. Results indicated that there was a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence. Moreover, resilience was significantly and positively correlated with emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence.

Rachel George et al. (2013)⁶, conducted a study to find out the relationship between Spiritual intelligence, Academic achievement and Teacher effectiveness among student teachers at elementary level. Results indicate that the teachers with high spiritual intelligence have an ability to reframe, and to see things in a wider context. This will embrace their holistic thinking and engages the whole person - teaching students to think critically and creatively for themselves.

Sabbal Patel et al. (2016)⁷, conducted a study to find out the relationship between Emotional Intelligence (EQ) & Spiritual Intelligence (SQ) of Higher Secondary Students in relation to High and Low Academic Achiever. The findings of the present study may be utilized by education policy planners in order to assess and modify their schemes, pertaining to the development of students. Education policy planners are more concern with input and output process.

Anandan Nair et al. (2017)⁸, conducted a study to find out the level of spiritual intelligence among higher secondary students. The results revealed that higher secondary students are having low level of Spiritual Intelligence. There is no significant difference in the Spiritual Intelligence among higher secondary school boys and girls.

2. Research Design

In this study the investigator followed simple sampling technique. The sample consisted of 300, secondary school students both boys and girls of Coimbatore District. It is not possible to conduct an investigation on the total population. Adequate representation has given to management and locality of the schools so that the sample would be a good representative of the population.

Factors taken into consideration while selecting the sample,

- 1) Gender-Male, Female
- 2) Location of Schools- Rural, Urban.
- 3) Type of Schools - Government, Government aided and Private.
- 4) Medium of instruction – Tamil, English
- 5) Religion – Hindu/Christians/Muslim /Others
- 6) Qualification – Father Qualification, Mother Qualification
- 7) Occupation – Father Occupation, Mother Occupation
- 8) Annual Income – Father Annual Income, Mother Annual Income

2.1. Tools Used in the Study

The Spiritual Intelligence Self-Report Inventory (SISRI-24) developed by King (2008). It consists of 24 items. It consists of 4 subscales namely: Critical Existential Thinking (CET), Personal Meaning Production (PMP), Transcendental Awareness (TA) and Conscious State Expansion (CSE). Scoring is based on five possible responses. Each score is given 0 to 4 for different responses. The item 6 should be scored in reverse order. Higher scores represent higher levels of spiritual intelligence and/or each capacity. The scale seems to be highly reliable and valid.

2.2. Descriptive Analysis

The arithmetic mean of male samples was 1.506 and for female samples it was 1.518. The higher mean value of female students indicates that they have higher spiritual intelligence compared to their male counterpart.

2.3. Differential Analysis

HYPOTHESIS 1: There is no significant difference between male and female students in their mean score of spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science. The calculated value (0.22) is less than the table value of 't' (1.98), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between male and female in their spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science

HYPOTHESIS 2: There is no significant difference towards Religion in their mean score of spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science. The calculated value of "F" (0.89) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 3.04, the Null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among religion with respect to spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science.

HYPOTHESIS 3: There is no significant difference towards Community in their mean score of spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science. The calculated value of "F" (0.85) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.40, the Null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among community with respect to spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science.

HYPOTHESIS 4: There is no significant difference towards educational qualification of father wise in their mean score of spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science. The calculated value of "F" (0.85) is less than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.42, the Null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among educational qualification of father with respect to spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science.

HYPOTHESIS 5: There is no significant difference towards educational qualification of mother wise in their mean score of spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science. The calculated value of "F" (3.37) is greater than the table value of "F" (0.05) which holds 2.42, the Null hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred from the above table that there is a significant difference among educational qualification of mother with respect to spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science.

HYPOTHESIS 6: There is no significant difference towards Occupation of father wise in their mean score of spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science. The calculated value of “F” (1.61) is less than the table value of “F” (0.05) which holds 2.42, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among occupation of father with respect to spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science.

HYPOTHESIS 7: There is no significant difference towards Occupation of mother wise in their mean score of spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science. The calculated value of “F” (1.61) is less than the table value of “F” (0.05) which holds 2.42, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among occupation of mother with respect to spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science.

HYPOTHESIS 8: There is no significant difference towards Annual income of father wise in their mean score of spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science. The calculated value of “F” (1.08) is less than the table value of “F” (0.05) which holds 2.42, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among annual income of father with respect to spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science.

HYPOTHESIS 9: There is no significant difference towards Annual income of mother wise in their mean score of spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science. The calculated value of “F” (0.95) is less than the table value of “F” (0.05) which holds 2.42, the Null hypothesis is accepted .It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among annual income of mother with respect to spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in science.

3. Conclusion

Based on the findings from the present study it was revealed that the higher mean value of female students indicates that they have higher spiritual intelligence compared to their male counterpart. The above findings are an original contribution to the existing knowledge and no such studies have been attempted in these selected dimensions. This study might enable teachers and administrators to look for ways of spiritual intelligence in relation to achievement in Science among secondary school students.

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